

DEVELOP CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS

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Abstract. The article describes the theoretical-methodological foundations of the development of creativity in students, including the level of scientific-theoretical study of the problem, pedagogical ways of developing creativity, criteria of pedagogue's creativity, existing theoretical and practical models of creativity development, and methods of improving the system of developing a creative person.

Keywords: development of creativity, theoretical-methodological foundations, scientific-theoretical, methodological foundations of the problem, pedagogical ways and criteria of pedagogue's creativity.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada talabalarda kreativlikni rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari, jumladan, muammoning ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan o'rganilganlik darajasi, kreativlikni rivojlantirishning pedagogik yo'llari, pedagogning kreativligi mezonlari, kreativlikni rivojlantirishning mavjud nazariy va amaliy modellar hamda ijodkor shaxsni rivojlantirish tizimini takomillashtirish usullari yoritib berilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: kreativlikni rivojlantirish, nazariy-metodologik asoslar, muammoning ilmiy-nazariy, metodologik asoslari, pedagogik yo'llari va pedagogning kreativligi mezonlari.

Аннотация В статье описаны теоретико-методологические основы развития креативности у студентов, в том числе уровень научно-теоретической изученности проблемы, педагогические пути развития креативности, критерии креативности педагога, существующие теоретические и практические модели развития креативности, методы. совершенствования системы развития творческой личности.

Ключевые слова: развитие творчества, теоретико-методологические основы, научно-теоретические, методологические основы проблемы, педагогические пути и критерии творчества педагога.

One of the main tasks of the modern education system, which helps to modernize the education system and fully adapt it to individual capabilities, is to determine and develop the qualities of initiative, independence, and creativity in students. From this point of view, one of the main conditions for the modernization of the system of training specialists, ensuring the effectiveness of pedagogical activity is to develop their creative attitude towards professional activity.

The foundation for the development of creativity is laid in childhood and is improved through education. The development of interest in creativity among students can be achieved only if it is carried out in harmony with the creation of a certain cultural environment, setting independent goals, understanding the meaning and essence of one's activities, and building

creativity. increases the demand and need for researching theoretical, and methodological foundations, pedagogical ways, and mechanisms. Creativity is manifested as an aesthetic, moral, national, ecological, legal, speech, work, and communication culture and represents the level of development of various abilities. It expresses the all-round development of a person, the ability to live in environmental conditions, and reflects the culture of society.

Scientists of the CIS have also dealt with issues related to creativity, the formation of cultural values of a person, creative ability, creative activity, and a systematic approach to the study of a person and managed to find various effective solutions in their research. For example, S.L. Rubinstein, T.A. Gartung, S.P. Osipenko, I.K. Studies by Shaylar et al.

Theoretical and practical models of filling cultural gaps that allow students to develop their creative abilities are revealed in the research of others. It is permissible to dwell on their separate scientific research, because, their research, was focused on the pedagogical possibilities of forming the creative abilities of modern students based on a creative approach, and on the identification of creativity as a component of the valuable direction of a teenager in pedagogical work.

Also, the concept of the creative approach as a source of personal and creative development of students (E.V. Bugakova, psychological conditions for the development of creativity of teenagers during the educational process (O.A. Khalifaeva, cognitive foundations of creativity (I.K. Shai) several scientific researches have been carried out.

A person develops and achieves progress through active creativity. Creativity expands the limits of human spiritual activity. A person acquires the status of a creator only through creative skills, and mental and physical work. Analyzing the conducted scientific research and researching the problem of their socialization through the formation of creativity in teenagers based on a creative approach, in this process, the harmonious application of existing technologies, psychological and pedagogical conditions, and opportunities for implementation in a creatively oriented educational environment. stipulates.

An analysis of the concepts underlying the interdependence of culture and education is presented in the following table:

The formation and development of a creative person depends on his adaptation to changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions, and human ontogenesis, that is, from birth to the end of his life, the content of activity that requires continuity and succession. This activity definitely determines the result of socialization of a person. In connection with prioritizing the creative capabilities of the individual for society, the main focus in modern education is to direct the child to freedom and individuality, self-control, openness to new ideas, and participation in creative games. It is considered appropriate to encourage aspects such as encouragement.

Creative thinking requires students to rely on many new and unusual ideas when completing educational tasks, problems, and tasks. That is, when solving a task or problem, the student looks for several options for a solution (multiple thinking), and then stops at one correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (unilateral thinking). Based on this, it can be said that students' creativity is manifested in their thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities, that is, creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics.

According to E.P. Torrens, he explains the concept of "creativity" from a scientific point of view as follows:

- putting forward scientific hypotheses or problems;
- checking and changing the hypothesis;
- identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results;
- sensitivity to the conflict between knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem.

Creative pedagogy reveals the possibilities of their effective use in the classroom by recommending strategies and tools that serve to stimulate the results of creative activity. In the process of studying creativity, the problems of forming the systems of intellectual and psychological development of general secondary school students were developed, and they are aimed at forming the components of the personal-creative way of thinking. The study of problems related to creative pedagogy, the creative potential of a person, and the conceptual foundations of creative education has become the object of several scientific research works.

A.A. Melik-Pashaev proves in his research that a child under the age of ten has more creative possibilities than a teenager or an adult. But the problem is that these abilities are not developed and disappear. Traditional education hinders the development of creativity and often leads to problems in the socialization of a person.

B. Yu. According to Bolshakov, only 3% of children who think creatively after completing general secondary education remain.

Existing analyses show that the necessary condition for the development of creative competence in students depends primarily on the creative potential of pedagogues. In particular, the initial condition and result of the student's creative activity is the teacher's creative competence.

In contrast to traditional pedagogical thinking, the ability to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the education and training process, and the ability to describe the readiness to positively solve existing pedagogical problems are the main criteria that determine the creativity of a pedagogue. These criteria represent the ability of teachers to express themselves creatively and the level of preparation for it. Due to the teacher's lack of creativity, students have interesting and wonderful ideas, but they are slow to express them. The reason for this is determined by the fact that the methods used in the educational process do not serve to form students' free and independent thinking skills. Nowadays, the ability to think creatively is necessary not only for students but for the future of every country. This is also true for teachers who implement the process because only a creative teacher can teach a creative student.

Mastering creative technologies of teaching allows teachers to model the learning process, introduce innovative creative technologies, approach each student individually, and increase their creative potential.

In conclusion, we can say that the use of vertical pedagogy in the process of education allows students to use the knowledge, skills, and qualifications they have acquired in their scientific activities. This prepares future teachers for pedagogical activities based on the competency approach.

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